

INNOVATIVE SCIENCE CLASSROOM: RESPONDING TO THE INVENTIVE THINKING SKILLS OF GRADE 12 STEM STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

One of the key attributes of successful teachers today is the ability to provide effective teaching in the age of technology. The new challenge is to acquire academic excellence within the context of today's technological environment in order to fully prepare students to thrive in the Digital Age. Thus, the researcher was greatly motivated to undertake this research aimed at determining whether relationship exists between the teacher's use of innovative science classroom and students' inventive thinking skills. The study used a descriptive research design utilizing the inventive thinking skills assessment rubric and innovative science classroom survey questionnaires as the main instruments in gathering data from 81 Grade 12 STEM students enrolled during the school year 2020-2021. The result shows that most of the respondents nearly acquired the inventive thinking skills after being exposed to innovative science classroom. Likewise, students perceived the innovative science classroom to be effective in terms of educational aspects. The findings of the present study however revealed that no significant relationship exists between the teacher's utilization of innovative science classroom and the level of students' inventive thinking skills. From these, the study suggests that further studies, especially those using experimental design, could be done in order to better explain the role of innovative science classroom in the development of students' inventive thinking.

Keywords: Innovative Science Classroom, Inventive Thinking Skills, Assessment Rubric, Digital Age